

PECULARITIES OF WRITING IN GERMAN LESSONS

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Astonova Guzalkhon Rakhmonalievna

German teacher of Fergana state university

Abstract.

This article is about developing writing skills. Pupils and students will be able to strengthen their knowledge through exercises about the development of writing skills.

Keywords.

foreign language, communication, vocabulary and grammar, essential information, certain structure, communicate differs, underestimate.

Writing is an elementary cultural technique and one of the basic skills. In writing, language is expressed in graphic symbols. Writing serves to record facts, opinions, thoughts, feelings, etc. in writing. The communication partner is not present and often not known. For foreign language teaching, writing is an important opportunity for contact with a foreign structure.

- Writing in DaF lessons

Writing has various functions in DaF lessons.

1. Purposefulness: The learner should be able to pass on information worth knowing to a communication partner (reader) while observing the usual conventions of the foreign language and foreign culture.

2. Supporting the language acquisition process (language learning): practicing and consolidating vocabulary and grammar, copying and editing texts, writing down essential information, etc. [1, 37 p]

- Writing as a goal and as a means

There are two different writing activities in DaF lessons:

1. Writing as a goal: e.g. when writing a letter, the goal of the action is a letter that you want to send to someone.

2. Writing as a means to an end: e.g. a certain structure is practiced in written grammar exercises.

- Writing as an intermediate skill

Writing serves as a means to an end, for example when a written grammar exercise serves to consolidate grammatical forms or when a certain vocabulary is practiced.

• Grammar exercises

In the textbook, which was created for the 9-10 classes of general education schools, the students practice the definite article, standing adjectives in the singular in the grammatically appropriate form, standing adjectives and possessive pronouns in the grammatically appropriate form. With these exercises, the students can not only practice, but also test their grammar knowledge while writing. [2, 106 p]

In the exercises given below, through association with nouns and adjectives, elementary school students will ask each other questions and recognize the adjectives. e.g.:

The sharp knife, the sharp needle, the delicious pudding, the sticky honey, the busy bee, the clever child.

Through the vocabulary exercise, the students develop good recognition when writing the flower names. e.g.:

In spring, many early bloomers bloom in our garden.

Lehrerzweigebest Grammatik

Was kannst du schon und wo hast du noch Übungsbedarf?

1. Ergänze bei folgenden Wörtern den bestimmten Artikel.

_____ Händchen, _____ Belastbarkeit, _____ Männlein, _____ Überlegung,
_____ Wohnzimmerisch, _____ Klavierlocker, _____ Fernsehgerät,
_____ Telefonanlage, _____ Briefzettelung, _____ Abstellkammerchen,
_____ Fußballmannschaft, _____ Akkuschrauber von 12 Punkten

2. Ergänze den fehlenden bestimmten Artikel und das in Klammern stehende Adjektiv im Singular in der grammatisch passenden Form.

a) Die Augen _____ (klein) Mädchen leuchten.
b) Sie schickt _____ (einsam) Frau eine Karte.
c) Er läuft _____ (verdächtig) Mann hinterher.
d) Die Hände _____ (rötend) Jungen baten sich zu Fäusten.
e) Sie liest _____ (umfangreich) Bedienungsanleitung.
f) Er fragt nach _____ (neu) Sekretärin.
g) _____ (ängstlich) Kätzchen flieht unter den Schrank.
h) Er findet _____ (müde) Sekretärin attraktiv. von 8 Punkten

3. Ergänze die in Klammern stehenden Possessivpronomen und Adjektive in der grammatisch passenden Form.

a) _____ (mein/klein) Schwester zieht nach Berlin.
b) Der Reißverschluss _____ (dein/blau) Jacke ist kaputt.
c) Ich überreiche _____ (sein/rot) Mutter das Geschenk.
d) Ich benutze _____ (dein/bist) Handy.
e) Er findet _____ (ih/golden) Kette am Boden.
f) _____ (unser/neu) Sonnenschirm ist schon kaputt.
g) Die Augen _____ (dein/jungen) Tochter sind braun.
h) Ich habe _____ (sein/tauglich) Tante eine Lügengeschichte outgetischt. von 8 Punkten

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13. Ausgabe

In conclusion, it can be said that writing serves to develop grammatical exercises, facts, opinions, thoughts, feelings.

A friendly contact between the teacher and the student is one of the foundations of learning. The teacher, who should not underestimate the contact, strengthens the children's will to learn and helps to achieve mutual (work) satisfaction. Good teaching is not only determined by the learning content, but also by well-functioning relationships. Students show greater willingness to learn motivation and will when they feel a personal interest in them as a person and when they recognize their teacher as an authority.

For respect, the teacher needs not only intellectual but also human qualities. If a teacher possesses both qualities and does not underestimate the importance of them, this forms the basis for success in the classroom.

The teacher must never forget his function as a role model and must also ensure that the children are treated well. Of course, every teacher has their own character and the way they communicate differs from teacher to teacher. However, the development of mutual relationships must always be in the foreground. It means with the children

to communicate.

Successful teaching and successful communication go hand in hand. An important part is also the common clear rules that should/should be fixed in class.

All these findings bring us to the conclusion that the following principles help to ensure a good teaching process:

- ✓ quality of the teacher
- ✓ mutual respect
- ✓ Good communication

- ✓ understanding of both parties
- ✓ clear rules

Before I get any further on this topic, I would like to make a small digression about the communicative competencies of the teacher. We experienced that the teacher forms the relationships in the class and that he has a big part in the communication.

The key competences are based on the development of the most important competences/characteristics of the personality. They are used in many subjects and situations.

Key general competencies include:

- ✓ communication
- ✓ Ability to resolve conflicts and problems
- ✓ Logical thinking
- ✓ leadership ability
- ✓ creativity
- ✓ motivation
- ✓ Teamwork
- ✓ ability to learn

A relationship develops between teachers and students that constantly changes over time. The good teacher should strive to create good relationships with and among students.

The teacher should not remain the only one. The students themselves also have a no less insignificant part in forming and shaping relationships in the class.

This is not the end of this knowledge. The next question, which we automatically come to here, is how such communication between teachers and students should look like? On what principles does communication in the class proceed?

Sides are interdependent as one cannot exist without the other. Communication takes place on the basis of certain relationships. These can be characterized as follows:

- ✓ teachers x students
- ✓ teacher x class
- ✓ teacher x group
- ✓ students x class
- ✓ students x group
- ✓ students x students
- ✓ group x group

✓ group x class

According to this pattern, the teacher not only communicates with the individual student, but also with the whole class or with the respective groups. Communication also occurs between students, between groups, and between the student and the class.

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